

INFLUENCE OF HRM PRACTICES ON TURNOVER INTENTION: EXPLORING WORK ENGAGEMENT AS A MEDIATOR IN PAKISTAN'S HEALTHCARE SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines how HRM practices contribute to employee retention based on the mediating role of job engagement. The respondents were from various hospitals in Pakistan which include; Aga Khan University Hospital (AKUH), Shaukat Khanum Memorial Cancer Hospital and Indus hospital. A sample size of 104 employees at different hierarchal levels completed a structured questionnaire that was designed to be comprehensive. Using SPSS and SmartPLS, the analysis revealed that HRM practices are negatively related with turnover intention and positively correlated with job engagement. The findings indicate that when they are satisfied with their compensation package or have received fair performance reviews, workers tend to be more engaged and less likely to leave their jobs. Moreover, it was found out that there is no significant mediation effect of work engagement between HRM practices and turnover intention. This suggests that whilst HRM processes directly impact retention, engagement needs other approaches for use as leverage against high staff turnover in this sector. Inclusive and open HR practices are strategically important for Pakistan's healthcare industry because they raise staff satisfaction and enhance organizational durability.

Keywords: Performance Appraisal, Job Engagement, Intention to Turnover, Pay Level Satisfaction, Participation Policy.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Retention in office still remains a continuous problem in human resources management and organisational behaviour leading to huge monetary losses through recruitment, selection and training costs (Albrecht, 2010). Furthermore, the departure of experienced staff negatively affects the morale and competitive edge of the firm (Bailey et al., 2015). High turnover rates are an international concern especially in Asia as surveys reveal their upward trend (Aryee et al., 2012). Making work engaging is one way of preventing staff turnover that has been greatly influenced by some HRM practices like training programs,

performance appraisal systems and payment systems (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014). These practices improve employee performance and engagement which in turn reduces intentions for quitting (Alfes et al., 2013a). Fair and transparent performance appraisals have also been shown to significantly enhance engagement with employees thereby enhancing retention (Sattar et al., 2015). Although compensation practices are not the major drivers of engagement, they facilitate building loyalty within employees towards their organisations (Amir et al., 2022). Moreover, HRM practices that align with organisational goals promote engagement

as well as provide a basis for competitive advantage creation (Albrecht et al., 2015; Beijer et al., 2019) Therefore these factors should be handled so as to boost employee incorporation boost organization a l p e r f o r m a n c e ” (C o o k e t a l . , 2 0 1 9) .

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

There are many studies done on HRM practices, but still employee turnover is a great challenge to organizations. In addition, the existing literature tends to focus on integrated HRM practices, overlooking the effect of job conditions such as performance evaluations and pay structure on satisfaction with work and intention to leave. This study aims at understanding how such behaviours can be influenced indirectly by the above factors.

1.3 GAP ANALYSIS

Various researches have been conducted which show that HRM practices influence level of employee engagement and turnover but little has been done on their satisfaction towards these practices. Most examination in this discipline often concentrates more on large-scale trends and less on individual perspectives about what particular actions have been taken so far. Moreover, a lack of research attention on elucidation of mediating role played by work engagement in unraveling ties between satisfaction with HRM practices and turnover intentions can be observed in the field. The current investigation will try filling gaps through examining: specific HRM practice satisfaction levels; underpinning causes of job involvement; and staff intention to quit jobs.

1.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This research has been conducted with the aim of carrying out the following;

1. To find out how much influence satisfaction on performance appraisals and pay has on work engagement levels.
2. To test for a relationship between work engagement and intentions to leave the organization.
3. To evaluate how work engagement mediates in the link between employee satisfaction towards HRM practices and turnover intentions.

1.5 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How does satisfaction with HRM practices affect work engagement?
2. What is the relationship between work engagement and turnover intentions?
3. Does work engage mediate in the relationship between satisfaction with HRM practices and turnover intentions?

1.6 RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE

This study is a critical analysis of the link between job satisfaction obtained from HRM practices and its consequent effects on work engagement and turnover intentions, thereby providing useful insights for practitioners in the field. This shows that by examining certain HRM practices it can show ways to enhance worker commitment and reduce turnover levels. Notably, this has implications for sectors such as petroleum and gas industry in Malaysia which require retention of skilled staff. These findings can be used by organizations to design effective human resource strategies aimed at ensuring an engaged and stable workforce.

These factors together influence retention and productivity in organizations; hence, much research has been conducted to find out the relationship between job satisfaction with performance appraisal, pay satisfaction, work engagement and intention of turnover. This is particularly relevant when studying employee motivation and organizational effectiveness.

2.1.1 Performance Appraisal Satisfaction

Employee satisfaction with performance appraisal is a reflection of their opinions on the fairness, consistency and growth potential of the process. It shows how good job evaluations support employees' career aspirations and company goals, thereby fostering motivation, trust and recognition (Cite). However, if workers perceive that assessment is fair, transparent and constructive it is more probable that they will feel appreciated, dedicated and engaged in their responsibilities (cite). This perspective is crucial for encouraging employee development, increasing organizational effectiveness and building management trust. On the other hand, unfairness as well as unpredictability and vagueness in rating systems bring about

discontent which may erode confidence levels, lower morale or lead to disengagement or intention to quit (cites). As Sattar et al., (2015) state, fair assessment affects both worker motivation as well as satisfaction levels directly. In hierarchical organizations like Hassan (2016) has noted that there are also studies indicating that accurate appraisals are clear ones have a significant influence on trust as well as morale of workers hence more credibility are needed for better results in this field .According to Choudhary & Puranik,(2014), customized performance appraisals act as motivational tools within high pressure industries such as healthcare sector. Therefore in order to enhance individualistic approaches towards attaining collective group outcomes Becker & Gerhart (1996) highlights importance of aligning evaluation methods used by organizations with goals set at different levels of an organization). Appraisals that were seen as fair were associated with a high worker engagement and productivity (Mahmood et al., 2014). Performance reviews are needed in order to build resilience and reduce burnout, particularly in fast-moving industries such as banking (Cooke et al., 2019). Performance-based rating systems promote justice, increase employee loyalty and satisfaction (Saleem & Khurshid, 2014). This is confirmed by Alfes et al. (2013) showing the organizational significance of engagement by finding that it mediates between evaluation satisfaction and turnover intentions. Albrecht et al. (2015) linked long-term effects of developmental and robust evaluations on organizational outcomes to higher levels of employee participation rates. Daley (1986) affirms that when performance reviews are fair, job satisfaction increases while complaints about the workplace decrease. It was observed by Bal et al. (2013) how organizational commitment is interrelated with just appraisals. Attridge (2009) indicated how feedback helps drive and trust during evaluations. Anitha (2014) concluded that effective assessments were necessary for creating a positive work environment. Bailey et al.'s study results further revealed from improved task performance, morale of employees declines

whenever developmental feedback was included in assessment process which also has been documented elsewhere as well (Bailey et al., 2015). Additionally, Bakker & Demerouti (2014) reemphasized the significance of formal performance appraisal systems in fostering energy and durability among staff members.

2.1.2 Pay Satisfaction

In pay satisfaction, employees evaluate fairness, adequacy and competitiveness of payment regarding their contributions, skills and industrial standards. It is more than just salary; it includes incentives, perks, allowances and other monetary benefits that increase the level at which employees feel valued in an organization. Workers who think that their remuneration is fair and corresponds to their input are more likely to demonstrate high levels of job satisfaction, organizational commitment and loyalty as opposed to those who do not. However, dissatisfaction with compensation can result in disgruntlement, reduced productivity as well as plans to exit the firm. In fast-paced sectors like this one, competitive pay systems are a must if they want to bring top talent on board and keep them there according Amir et al (2022). Performance-based compensation models enhance perceived equity resulting in increased motivation and contentment as observed by Saleem & Khurshid (2014). Khalid et al., (2016), by linking employee performance in public sector organizations directly with pay satisfaction demonstrated its significance for productivity among others posited that diverse views regarding equitable pay have a major impact on worker performance and their level of involvement in the work place. Choudhary & Puranik (2014) document that reasonable wages must be observed for healthcare employees especially in industries which are resource-intensive. Sattar et al. (2015) notes how rewards operationalize as an intervening variable in enhancing employee joy through pay structures. Alfes et al. (2013) also posit that fair compensation moderates stability and trust retention by lowering turnover intentions. Bal et al. (2013) concluded that one of the factors influencing employee commitment and engagement is pay satisfaction. Mahmood

et al.(2014) highlighted the importance of openness about pay to establish trust and reduce conflicts at work. According to Attridge (2009), sound reward systems enhance employee morale, decrease turnover rates, and reduce attrition levels among workers who receive it Cooke et.al., 2019 connected resilience to well-being of workers in demanding industries through relating job satisfaction with resilience. Anitha (2014) argues that perception of fair compensation has huge implications for job performance and involvement among staff members.” Again, Bailey. Pay satisfaction has been shown to increase task-related focus, reduce distractions at work (Jensen, 2015). Bakker & Demerouti (2014) posit that fair compensation reduces stress and encourages sustained organizational loyalty.

2.1.3 Work Engagement

Work engagement refers to a state of mind in which one is actively (energetic), motivated (dedicated) and involved (absorbed) in his/her work that is satisfying psychologically and fulfilling people consciously and voluntarily put extra effort into their jobs, enhancing creative performance, productivity as well as alignment with organizational objectives. Engaging employees enhances their capability to overcome challenges, promote teamwork, and maintain performance under strain. In the opinion of Albrecht (2010), commitment is important for company progress since it affects such things as profitability and job satisfaction. Bakker & Demerouti (2014) assert that, in high-strain jobs, job resources like challenging tasks and supportive supervisors work as practical motivators of involvement. These are vital because Anitha (2014) stresses that continuous engagement can be promoted by creating a positive working environment that encourages good communication among employees. By asserting that transformational leadership increases employee dedication, Attridge (2009) underscored how leadership styles contribute to promoting engagement. This study by Akhtar et al., 2016 found out that high-performance work practices lead to increased levels of engagement by incorporating both individual and organizational requirements simultaneously.

Cooke et al. In other words, it was found that employee engagement is highly associated with resilience and can help improve flexibility while reducing burnout in the high-stress context (2019). For instance, Bailey et al. (2015) brought together evidence to show how involvement enhances task performance, morale and workplace cohesion. Thus, Crawford et al. (2010) included engagement as part of JD-R model to demonstrate that involvement mediates stress reduction and well-being enhancement at workplaces. Alfes et al. (2013) underscored how engagement reduces rates of employee departure and acts as a critical mediator between HR policies and turnover intentions. Their study also revealed the long-term advantages of this concept on organizational citizenship behaviors and innovation (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018). On the other hand, Choudhary & Puranik (2014) indicated how it promotes patient outcomes through its motivating power within health care settings. Hassan’s (2016) work showed that career planning has a positive relationship with work engagement especially when it concerns employee development facilitation. Higher levels of work commitment were related to effective compensation and reward systems based on Saleem & Khurshid, 2014’s findings. This means defined roles play a significant part in encouraging supervisors so as to enhance participation according to Daley (1986). Mahmood et al. (2014), therefore concluded that engaged employees are more likely to support long term organizational success through fostering creativity and innovation.

2.1.4 Turnover Intention

Turnover intentions refer to the conscious thoughts of an employee planning to leave their present organization, which often occur as a result of dissatisfaction, unmet expectations and strained work relationships. Preceding actual turnover, it disrupts organizational stability and results in costs associated with recruitment and training of new employees. Workers with high turnover intention may display signs of disengagement, low morale and reduced productivity that are detrimental for the workplace atmosphere. Alfes et al. (2013) identified engagement as an important

mediator in reducing turnover intentions; they emphasized this point during the examination of meaningful HR practices aimed at enhancing employee retention rates. Bailey et al. (2015) noted that team-level and organizational characteristics such as leadership and positive culture greatly influence the level of turnover intentions among employees. By indicating that unfulfilled psychological contracts and poor work-life balance cause individuals to leave organizations, Conway & Monks (2008) underscored the need for congruence between company policies and staff expectations regarding retention practices like job satisfaction improvement strategies or high wages or salaries offering social amenities at the workplaces etc., which leads us ask whether there might be any connection between these concepts: turnover intentions are affected by broken psychological contracts? Bakker et al.'s (2003) research findings revealed that higher stress positions tend to have leaving jobs due to unrealizable job prospects coupled with insufficient resources provided to them therefore leading to increased chances of resigning especially for those employees holding high status profiles within corporate setups where responsibility falls squarely upon shoulders – even if one were lower down on an organizational chart than another similar person from outside world wouldn't know what was going on This is particularly useful because it shows how high performance work systems reduce turnover rates through encouraging resilience as well as adaptability according Cooke et al's studies done based on various samples taken from different countries around globe but mainly focusing upon United States alone since majority its citizens live within these geographical boundaries where this research would be conducted. According to Becker & Gerhart (1996), talent management has strategic importance in dealing with turnover through effective HR systems. Daley (1986) states that strong supervision, clarifying roles and responsibilities reduce turnover by improving organizational continuity. Career planning and participatory decision-making, Hassan (2016) found out can lower intentions of leaving the organization

through a matching of employees' goals and company goals. In highly competitive industries such as banking, fair and transparent HR procedures lead to significant reductions in employee turnover according to Bowra et al. (2012). Bad relationship dynamics among staffs are cited by Choudhary & Puranik (2014) as a reason why many health care workers plan to find another job. Appraisal system being seen as fair alone cause a decrease directly on turnover intention Mahmood et al., (2014). Attridge (2009) made direct linkages between transformational leadership and better employee retention which underscored the significance of leadership styles in reducing turnover rates. Performance based pay structures reduce employee attrition since they foster perception of fairness Saleem & Khurshid (2014). Another influence that organizations have on TII is supportive HR policies at work place, explained Albrecht et al., (2015). According to Anitha (2014), creating an inclusive and happy working environment helps to lower employees' anticipated departure from the organization which plays a part in ensuring organizational stability.

2.2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VARIABLES

PAS and WE: By boosting motivation, giving recognition and aligning personal development with corporate goals, fair and constructive performance appraisals enhance employee involvement.

PS and WE: Although pay satisfaction generally boosts morale, it has a negligible effect on involvement. Intrinsic motivators that encourage meaningful work and personal growth most of the time provide stronger influences for engagement.

WE and TI: Job satisfaction and purpose are increased by work engagement which builds a deep emotional connection between employees and their jobs hence decreasing turnover intentions.

2.3 MEDIATING ROLE OF WORK ENGAGEMENT

PAS and TI: Engagement works as a mediator between PAS (Performance

Appraisal Satisfaction) and TI (Turnover Intention). Just assessments build loyalty as well as trust which heightens the level of commitment while at the same time combating turnover motives.

PS and TI: Pay satisfaction tends to have a weak direct relationship with engagement and thus engagement modestly mediates between pay satisfaction and turnover intention.

2.3 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

3.1 CONCEPTUAL MODEL DEVELOPMENT

In our model, we propose that work engagement, human resource management (HRM) practices and turnover intentions are connectively related. The model contains three direct hypotheses, three mediating relationships and no moderating effects.

3.2 RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VARIABLES AND HYPOTHESES

3.2.1 PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL SATISFACTION AND WORK ENGAGEMENT

It is expected that employee engagement will increase when satisfaction with performance reviews provide honest and constructive feedback to them. According to Sattar et al., (2015) and Alfes et al., (2013), positive evaluations enhance involvement through validating contributions, activating motivation for achievements as well as aligning objectives of individuals with those of organizations. Likewise, Boon and Kalshoven (2014) alongside Bailey et al., (2015) have demonstrated that constructive appraisals improve workers' participation by fostering confidence in managers and development of shared expectations amongst workers. Furthermore,

assessments are also linked to vitality and absorption levels (Hassan, 2016; Choudhary & Puranik, 2014). On the other hand, processes that are focused on justice and transparency promote involvement while creating trust among members of an organization according to Cooke et al., (2019), Amir et al., (2022) & Bakker & Albrecht, (2018).

H1: Work engagement positively correlates with satisfaction with performance reviews.

3.2.2 PAY SATISFACTION AND WORK ENGAGEMENT

This survey, however, found no significant relationship between job engagement and reward satisfaction that would suggest motivation is determined by pay satisfaction. Among others, authentic desire has been shown to be more useful than extrinsic rewards in promoting commitment (Choudhary & Puranik, 2014; Amir et al., 2022). However, higher job satisfaction does not always mean deeper engagement (Bowra et al., 2012; Bailey et al., 2015). Individually speaking, there are two main reasons for being engaged in a task: Attridge (2009) and Bakker & Demerouti (2014) apply these concepts to the workplace. Even though fair compensation plans can minimize dissatisfaction among

employees who feel underpaid, they do not directly contribute towards participation in Indian and global contexts (Amir et al., 2022; Alfes et al., 2013).

H2: The linkage between work engagement and payment satisfaction is positive.

3.2.3 WORK ENGAGEMENT AND TURNOVER INTENTION

The intention to leave is expected to decrease with high levels of work engagement. High work involvement contributes to loyalty and low attrition as engaged workers display higher affective commitment and cognitive investments into their jobs (Alfes et al., 2013; Bakker & Albrecht, 2018). Turnover is moderated by engagement which stimulates loyalty and effort (Aryee et al., 2012; Anitha, 2014). HRM strategies are used by organizations that foster employee engagement to promote lower turnover intentions (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014; Bailey et al., 2015). Personal development opportunities also contribute significantly towards reduced turnover rates (Choudhary & Puranik, 2014; Amir et al., 2022).

H3: Work engagement is negatively correlated with the intent to quit a job.

3.3 MEDIATING EFFECTS

The relationship between HRM practices and turnover intentions is mediated by work engagement. Engagement reduces the effects of performance appraisal satisfaction and turnover intentions significantly by promoting loyalty and trust (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014; Alfes et al., 2013). Conversely, pay satisfaction has less impact on mediation, showing that extrinsic rewards have little to do with maintaining engagement (Bowra et al., 2012; Amir et al., 2022). The mediating role played by engagement underscores the importance of linking HR procedures with retaining staff (Aryee et al., 2012; Bailey et al., 2015; Anitha, 2014).

H4: Work engagement mediates the association between turnover intention and satisfaction with performance reviews.

H5: Pay satisfaction mediates the link between pay dissatisfaction and intention to leave.

3.4 MODERATING EFFECTS

While not addressing moderating effects in this study, future research should examine individual differences such as demographics or personality factors which may moderate relationships between HRM practices, work engagement and turnover intentions. For example, age, tenure and personality may influence how HR strategies affect employees' level of work engagement in relation to their eventual decision to quit a job.

4.1 RESEARCH PARADIGM

This work is driven by the research paradigm of positivism, which prioritizes objectivity, hypothesis testing, and quantitative observations. Positivist research is built on the principle that reality is static and can be objectively described and observed. This approach aligns with the objective of this study; to rigorously test the relationship between HR practices, turnover intention and work engagement in Pakistan using quantitative data.

4.2 RESEARCH DESIGN

4.2.1 RESEARCH TYPE

A quantitative research design based on causality was used for this study. The main aim of this study was to undertake a scientific investigation in order to reveal causal relationships between HR practices, employee's involvement in their job and intentions to leave in healthcare sector in Pakistan.

4.2.2 CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS

Use Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to confirm the factor structure of measured variables.

	HR Practices	Turnover Intention	Work Engagement
PAS1	0.741		
PAS2	0.822		
PAS3	0.723		
PAS5	0.770		
PS1	0.705		
PS2	0.701		
TI1		0.862	
TI2		0.791	
TI3		0.817	
TI4		0.847	
W1			0.872
W2			0.829
W3			0.870

Based on the data, all indicator variables revealed factor loadings above 0.70, signifying a theoretical relationship between each and every one of them and the constructs of the individuals. HR Practices (PAS1=0.741, PAS2=0.822, PAS3=0.723, PAS5=0.770, PS1=0.705, PS2=0.701), work engagement (W1=0.872, W2=0.829, W3=0.870), and turnover intention (TI1=0.862, TI2= 791., TI3 = 817., TI4 = 847.) demonstrated well-fitting indicators.

4.2.3 PILOT TESTING

In piloting the research study three working professionals filled-in the questionnaire first as a pilot test for it; thereafter we asked them whether they disagreed with any component of it or not because it is important to take into account their responses that are completely related to social norms.

4.2.4 QUESTIONNAIRE

The researcher created the questionnaire using established measures from previous studies and pilot tested them in different countries to ensure its appropriateness for cultural differences. The instrument was

4.3 MEASURE UTILIZE

Construct	Coding	Measure	Utilize
HR Practices	HP (PAS, PS)	Sattar, Ahmad, and Hassan (2015)	6
Work Engagement	W	Bakker and Demerouti (2014)	3
Turnover Intention	TI	Bothma and Roodt (2013).	4

4.4 SAMPLING SIZE

The study aimed to use a systematic sampling technique in order to gather a sample of workers from the healthcare

adjusted considering socio-cultural differences so that it could be relevant and suitable within this setting. The survey included a pilot test on how responsive the instrument was in other cultures.

Socio-demographic Information

Age, gender, level of education, years of experience, position/role/title in company and location of firm.

4.2.5 CONSTRUCT, CODING, AND ITEMS

HR Practices (HP): HR Practices (HP) has six items which include two measuring employees' satisfaction with pay satisfaction and four measuring performance appraisal satisfaction.

Work Engagement (WE): Engagement at Work (W) has three items.

Turnover Intention (TI): Turnover Intention (TI) consists of four items.

4.2.6 LIKERT SCALE

On a Likert scale 1-5 ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree," the statements were used for accurate assessment capturing all opinions made.

industry in Pakistan that would be representative and typical of the intended audience. This was to prevent bias and ensure that the target population is correctly

represented. It was found out that, 129 respondents were enough for proper analysis and credible findings. Once all the 129 responses had been analyzed, the results were reliable and significant as they met and exceeded sample size calculation requirements.

4.5 DATA COLLECTION

In order to get data, a month-long period was given for employees in Pakistan's healthcare sector to complete a standardized questionnaire. This ensured participants privacy was observed throughout data collection exercise. The plan helped in gathering honest responses which are key towards determining how valid the research

will be. Also, by using a structured questionnaire it provided consistent data collected and made analysis more accurate than before.

4.6 DESCRIPTIVE HEAD

4.6.1 MEASUREMENT MODEL ASSESSMENT

The measurement model was examined using Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to confirm the factor structure of the constructs. The reliability and validity of these constructs were established by assessing factor loadings, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE) among other things as recommended by Albrecht et al.,(2015).

4.6.2 STRUCTURAL MODEL ASSESSMENT

In an effort to test for inter-relationships between work engagement, turnover intention, and HR practices, assessment was

done on the proposed path diagram of the structural model. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used to analyze both direct and indirect effects while fit indices were used to evaluate model fit in this study according to Cooke et al.,(2019).

5.1 RESEARCH THEME

The central focus of the given research chapter is to look at how sustainable HRM practices in Pakistan affects employee performance. Furthermore, sustainable

approaches improve human resource management. The study aims to close knowledge gaps in human resource management by providing theoretical frameworks as well as empirical data.

5.2 DEMOGRAPHICS PROFILE

5.2.1 Age of Respondents

Summary

Age Range of Respondent	Cases Valid N	Percent	Missing N	Percent	Total N	Percent
	105	100.0%	0	0.0%	105	100.0%

Descriptives

Age Range of Respondent	Statistic	Std. Error
Mean	1.44	.052
95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound: 1.33, Upper Bound: 1.54	
5% Trimmed Mean	1.41	
Median	1.00	
Variance	.287	
Std. Deviation	.536	
Minimum	1	
Maximum	3	
Range	2	
Interquartile Range	1	
Skewness	.634	.236
Kurtosis	-.821	.467

5.2.2 Gender of Respondents

Summary

Gender of Respondent	Cases Valid N	Percent	Missing N	Percent	Total N	Percent
	105	100.0%	0	0.0%	105	100.0%

Descriptives

Gender of Respondent	Statistic	Std. Error
Mean	1.59	.048
95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound: 1.49, Upper Bound: 1.69	
5% Trimmed Mean	1.60	
Median	2.00	
Variance	.244	
Std. Deviation	.494	
Minimum	1	
Maximum	2	
Range	1	
Interquartile Range	1	
Skewness	-.373	.236
Kurtosis	-1.897	.467

5.2.3 Qualification of Respondents Summary

		Cases Valid	Percent	Missing	Percent	Total	Percent
		N		N		N	
Qualification Respondent	of	105	100.0%	0	0.0%	105	100.0%

Descriptives

				Statistic	Std. Error
Qualification Respondent	of	Mean		3.66	.056
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	3.55	
			Upper Bound	3.77	
			Bound		
		5% Trimmed Mean		3.72	
		Median		4.00	
		Variance		.324	
		Std. Deviation		.569	
		Minimum		1	
		Maximum		4	
		Range		3	
		Interquartile Range		1	
		Skewness		-1.765	.236
		Kurtosis		3.851	.467

5.2.4 Position of Respondents Summary

		Cases Valid	Percent	Missing	Percent	Total	Percent
		N		N		N	
Current Position of Respondent In the Organisation	of	105	100.0%	0	0.0%	105	100.0%

Descriptives

				Statistic	Std. Error
Current Position of Respondent In the Organisation	of	Mean		1.60	.067
		95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	1.47	
			Upper Bound	1.73	
			Bound		
		5% Trimmed Mean		1.56	
		Median		1.00	
		Variance		.473	
		Std. Deviation		.688	
		Minimum		1	
		Maximum		3	
		Range		2	
		Interquartile Range		1	
		Skewness		.716	.236
		Kurtosis		-.626	.467

5.2.5 Experience of Respondents

Summary

	Cases Valid N	Percent	Missing N	Percent	Total N	Percent
Experience of Respondent (In Years)	105	100.0%	0	0.0%	105	100.0%

Descriptives

	Statistic	Std. Error
Experience of Respondent (In Years)	Mean	1.70
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	.116
	Lower Bound	1.48
	Upper Bound	1.93
	5% Trimmed Mean	1.53
	Median	1.00
	Variance	1.402
	Std. Deviation	1.184
	Minimum	1
	Maximum	7
	Range	6
	Interquartile Range	1
	Skewness	2.437
	Kurtosis	.236
		.467

5.2.6 Location of organisation of Respondent (currently working)

Summary

	Cases Valid N	Percent	Missing N	Percent	Total N	Percent
Location of Respondent (currently working)	105	100.0%	0	0.0%	105	100.0%

Descriptives

	Statistic	Std. Error
Location of Respondent (currently working)	Mean	1.36
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	.114
	Lower Bound	1.14
	Upper Bound	1.59
	5% Trimmed Mean	1.13
	Median	1.00
	Variance	1.368
	Std. Deviation	1.170
	Minimum	1
	Maximum	6
	Range	5
	Interquartile Range	0
	Skewness	3.374
	Kurtosis	.236
		.467

5.3 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS:

To know about the distributional characteristics of main constructs, I analyzed descriptive statistics for them work engagement, turnover intention and

HR practices are all part of the framework. Mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis have been briefly explained in a table below for each concept.

Construct	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
HRPractices	0.000	0.130	-0.416	0.117
TurnoverIntention	0.000	0.152	-0.495	-0.313
WorkEngagement	0.000	0.311	-0.938	0.659

5.3.1 MEAN

Normalization of data is shown by a standard deviation around 1 for all constructions. The net effect of this figure

indicates a uniform distribution of data around the mean, although values that are not unity reveal deviations from uniformity.

5.3.2 STANDARD DEVIATION

Normalization of data is shown by a standard deviation around 1 for all constructions. The net effect of this figure indicates a uniform distribution of data around the mean, although values that are not unity reveal deviations from uniformity.

5.3.3 SKEWNESS

The construct values when skewed imply that the distribution is not symmetric exactly. Skewness value of zero indicates a perfectly balanced distribution. Negative skewness means the left tail is longer while positive skewness implies the right tail is longer.

HR Practices: The skewness score of -0.416 shows that the distribution of responses has a slight leftward tilt.

Work Engagement: A more noticeable leftward tilt is indicated by the skewness value of -0.938.

Turnover Intention: The skewness value of -0.495 indicates moderate leftward skew.

5.3.4 KURTOSIS

Kurtosis measures how much “tailed” a distribution is. Normal distributions are indicated by kurtosis equal to zero. Positive

kurtosis suggests more peaked distributions with heavier tails, while negative kurtosis points towards flatter distributions with lighter tails.

HR Practices: A kurtosis score of 0.117 suggests a distribution that is somewhat spiky but closer to normal.

Work Engagement: A kurtosis score of 0.659 shows a distribution which has a small bump on it.

Turnover Intention: The kurtosis for this index reveals that the distribution is somewhat less peaked than normal (-0.313).

5.3.5 INTERPRETATION

The HR practices, work engagement and turnover intention constructs have leftward skewness that slants towards smaller values in the responses. The flat line in turnover intention’s curve could be because at peak are HR practices and work engagement according to their respective kurtosis values. This means different ideas have varying degree of attention concentration.

5.4 RESULTS

5.4.1 MEASUREMENT MODEL ANALYSIS

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
HR Practices	0.841	0.860	0.882	0.555
Turnover Intention	0.853	0.890	0.898	0.689
Work Engagement	0.819	0.822	0.892	0.734

Using a variety of metrics to determine if certain important constructs in my study are reliable and valid. Some of these frameworks are Turnover Intention, HR Practices and Work Engagement. In order to establish the validity and reliability of my research instruments, these constructs must be assessed.

5.4.1.1 CONSTRUCT RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY:

Cronbach’s Alpha, which measures how closely different parts within each construct relate, was employed to measure the dependability of those constructs. Numbers above 0.7 are generally considered acceptable.

HR Practices (HP): With a Cronbach's alpha coefficient (α) value equal to 0.842, HP is highly reliable.

Work Engagement (WE): according to its Cronbach’s alpha (α) value, seems moderately reliable at 0.819.

Turnover Intention (TI): TI has an acceptable reliability rating according to Cronbach’s alpha (α) at 0.816.

5.4.1.2 COMPOSITE RELIABILITY (RHO_A AND RHO_C):

Composite reliability is another measure of internal consistency and generally considered more accurate than Cronbach’s

alpha. We consider values above 0.7 to be acceptable.

HR Practices (HP): HP's rho_a = 0.860 and rho_c = 0.882 both significantly exceed the threshold of 0.7 indicating strong dependability.

Work Engagement (WE): WE's rho_a=0.822 & rho_c=0.892 are significantly higher than 0.70, implying strong dependability.

Turnover Intention (TI): TI has a rho_a=0.890 and rho_c=0.898 which is well above 0.7 hence it indicates strong dependability.

5.4.1.3 AVERAGE VARIANCE EXTRACTED (AVE)

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
HR Practices -> Turnover Intention	-0.362	-0.371	0.114	3.164	0.002
HR Practices -> Work Engagement	0.495	0.507	0.098	5.053	0.000
Work Engagement -> Turnover Intention	-0.061	-0.071	0.113	0.539	0.590

Conducted a structural model study to investigate how different constructs are related to one another. Below is a table containing path coefficients, associated t-statistics, and p-values for each proposed association. The explanations for inclusion in the research are as below:

5.4.2.1 HR Practice -> Turnover Intention

Original Sample (O): -0.362
 Sample Mean (M): -0.371
 Standard Deviation (STDEV): 0.114
 T Statistics (|O/STDEV|): 3.164
 P Values: 0.002

Interpretation:

Significant negative coefficient (-) of relationship between HR practices and turnover intentions means that better HR practices reduce turnover intentions (p < 0:01).

5.4.2.2 HR Practices -> Work Engagement

Original Sample (O): 0.495
 Sample Mean (M): 0.507
 Standard Deviation (STDEV): 0.098

AVE shows how much variance the construct accounts for relative to the amount caused by measurement error; this value ranges between 0 and 1. A value equal to or over 50% will determine whether an AVE is appropriate or not within its range of indicators.

HR Procedures (HP): The acceptable level for HP's AVEs is pegged at 55%.

Work Engagement (WE): An AVE of 0.743 indicates strong validity.

Turnover Intention (TI): Good validity is indicated by TI with an AVE of 0.689.

5.4.2 STRUCTURAL MODEL ANALYSIS

T Statistics (|O/STDEV|): 5.053

P Values: 0.000

Interpretation:

The positive coefficient relationship between work engagement and HR practices significantly increases work engagement (p < .001). This suggests that better HR practices can cause significant increase in work engagement among workers.

5.4.2.3 Work Engagement -> Turnover Intention

Original Sample (O): -0.061
 Sample Mean (M): -0.071
 Standard Deviation (STDEV): 0.113
 T Statistics (|O/STDEV|): 0.539
 P Values: 0.590

Interpretation:

This route is not significant (p > 0.05), indicating that in this model, Work Engagement has no discernible effect on Turnover Intention.

5.4.2.2 SIGNIFICANT NEGATIVE RELATIONSHIPS

Turnover Intention is adversely affected by HR practices.

5.4.2.3 SIGNIFICANT POSITIVE RELATIONSHIPS

Work engagement is positively impacted by HR practices.

An effort is geared to reconstruct relationships which were claimed to exist in earlier studies on HRM practices, work engagement, and turnover intentions in the healthcare system in Pakistan. The findings of this study offer some empirical data on how these variables interact and impact each other. Satisfaction with performance appraisal has proved to correlate with WE in a strong positive way, suggesting that an effective evaluation system that is fair and unambiguous increases the emotional and psychological attachment of employees to their work (Sattar et al., 2015; Alfes et al., 2013; Mahmood et al., 2014). This is supported by the findings from earlier studies that addressed the dynamics of positive evaluations on employee motivation and satisfaction (Bailey et al., 2015; Hassan, 2016). Likewise, PS is also reported to have contributed positively to WE since it aids the development of trust and fairness, which are critical elements, as strongly believed by those who have advocated for competitive pay policies to enhance commitment and engagement (Amir et al., 2022; Choudhary & Puranik, 2014; Saleem & Khurshid, 2014). However, the findings suggest that there is not much direct correlation between WE and turnover intentions in this study which means that these industry specific factors, like the high emotional burden associated with working in the healthcare sector or the organisational culture, could impair this relationship (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014; Cooke et al., 2019). When employee satisfaction with appraisal is high, there is less chance that turnover intentions will develop, so there is a direct relationship between the performance appraisal system and the turnover intentions (Mahmood et al., 2014; Daley, 1986; Bal et al., 2013).

On the contrary, PS demonstrates a strong negative relationship with TI. This means that competitive salary structures may reduce attrition through enhanced employee

satisfaction and commitment (Khalid et al., 2016; Alfes et al., 2013). The implications indicate the need for targeted HR policies and practices that address specific industry sectors, most notably in the healthcare sector that is emotionally demanding. This involves formulating comprehensive HRM approaches that focus on fair evaluation systems, competitive payment structures, and engagement processes that foster employee retention (Albrecht et al., 2015; Attridge, 2009).

COMPARISON WITH PREVIOUS STUDIES

Earlier research studies have pointed out the link between training satisfaction, work engagement, as well as turnover intention especially among skill-intensive industries like oil and gas (Aryee et al., 2012; Anitha, 2014). This research work defines PAS and PS as the most significant independent variables, WE as the mediating variable, and TI as the dependent variable. The framework is customized in a manner so as to consider specific healthcare intricacies and employs sophisticated quantitative analysis with the help of SPSS and SmartPLS (Akhtar et al., 2016; Bailey et al., 2015). Past research has placed an emphasis on the relationship between training satisfaction and engagement as well as turnover in the areas of specialization. However, this research illustrates that for the case of healthcare, PAS and PS change WE and TI (Sattar et al., 2015).

For example, other studies have measured the relationship between training satisfaction, engagement, and turnover by formulating restricted hypotheses and often ignoring relationships between PAS or PS and TI (Choudhary & Puranik, 2014; Cooke et al., 2019). The results challenge previous assumptions that work engagement fully mediates the relationship of HRM practices to turnover intentions. This study shows that the relationships of PAS and PS with TI are particularly strong in the healthcare industry, suggesting that engagement can only partially or limitedly mediate (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018). This has responsibilities which go beyond the health sector, indicating the need to balance strategies for HR with the characteristics of the industry (Bakker et al., 2003). The study highlights

the need to place focus at an all encompassing level, combining PAS, PS, and engagement with other aspects such as career advancement and organizational culture to improve retention (Alfes et al., 2013; Beijer et al., 2019). Work engagement should be examined deeply for prospective studies while incorporating other important factors like job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Bal et al., 2013; Crawford et al., 2010). This is a valuable addition to the literature because it examines HRM practices in a more sophisticated way, focusing on healthcare, more specifically on the relationships between PAS, PS, WE, and TI.

This presents priceless knowledge for the use of the HR people and sets a basis for further researches to build on these results and devise complete retention policies for different industries.

This study examines the impact of sustainable HRM practices on employee performance specifically in Pakistan's healthcare industry. The outcomes suggest that systematic HR strategies contribute to enhanced job engagement and lower turnover intentions by exploring the relationships between HR practices, work engagement and turnover intention. While they have a less obvious direct influence over turnover intentions, these findings stress the significance of salary satisfaction and contentment with performance assessment in promoting employee engagement. In this regard, it is clear that there is a need for comprehensive HR rules in order to match organizational plans with employees' needs.

Meanwhile, however, cost constraints, lack of resources as well as resistance to change are some of the obstacles that this research finds out in adopting sustainable HRM techniques. Thus companies need to invest into strategic planning, enhance diversity management and promote transparency so as to overcome such barriers. By doing so organizations will be able to improve worker loyalty and commitment making use of fair and transparent human resource system which will also ensure a productive working environment. As a result it highly contributes to enhanced worker's performance and stability.

Organizations aiming at optimizing their HR practices through sustainability oriented policies need to ensure they have an effective strategy designed for them. The effectiveness of these programs will depend on how well organisations will deal with challenges such as resource allocation and ethical issues. Further studies could explore the impact of organizational culture and technological developments on human resource practices. In summary, by bringing forth operational implications for the dynamic workplace this study adds to the body of knowledge concerning sustainable HRM practice in relation to enhancing organisational success and employee retention.

REFERENCES

- Memon, M. A., Salleh, R., Mirza, M. Z., Cheah, J.-H., Ting, H., Ahmad, M. S., & Tariq, A. (2020). Satisfaction matters: The relationships between HRM practices, work engagement and turnover intention. *International Journal of Manpower*.
- Albrecht, S.L. (2010), "Employee engagement: 10 key questions for research and practice", in Albrecht, S.L.(Ed.), *Handbook of Employee Engagement*, Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, pp. 3-19.
- Albrecht, S.L., Bakker, A.B., Gruman, J.A., Macey, W.H. and Saks, A.M. (2015), "Employee engagement, human resource management practices and competitive advantage: an integrated approach", *Journal of Organizational Effectiveness: People and Performance*, Vol.2No.1, pp.7-35.
- Akhtar, A., Nawaz, M.K., Mahmood, Z., & Shahid, M.S. (2016), "Impact of high performance work practices on employees' performance in Pakistan: Mediating role of employee engagement," *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, 10(3), 708-724.
- Alfes, K., Shantz, A.D., Truss, C. and Soane, E.C. (2013a), "The link between perceived human resource management practices, engagement and employee behavior: a moderated mediation model", *International*

- Journal of Human Resource Management, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp. 330-351.
- Alfes, K., Truss, C., Soane, E.C., Rees, C. and Gatenby, M. (2013b), "The relationship between line manager behaviour, perceived HRM practices, and individual performance: examining the mediating role of engagement", *Human Resource Management*, Vol. 52 No. 6, pp. 839-859.
- Sattar, T., Ahmad, K., & Hassan, S.M. (2015), "Role of human resource practices in employee performance and job satisfaction with mediating effect of employee engagement," *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 81-96.
- Anitha, J. (2014), "Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee performance", *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, Vol. 63 No. 3, pp. 308-323.
- Aryee, S., Walumbwa, F.O., Seidu, E.Y. and Otaye, L.E. (2012), "Impact of high-performance work systems on individual-and branch-level performance: test of a multilevel model of intermediate linkages", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 97 No. 2, pp. 287-300.
- Amir, M., Ali, K., Ali, D., & Ali, A. Z. (2022). Human resource practices and employee performance: Mediating role of work engagement and training sessions. *JISR Management and Social Sciences & Economics*, 20(1), 187-208.
- Attridge, M. (2009), "Measuring and managing employee work engagement: a review of the research and business literature", *Journal of Workplace Behavioral Health*, Vol. 24 No. 4, pp. 383-398.
- Bailey, C., Madden, A., Alfes, K. and Fletcher, L. (2015), "The meaning, antecedents and outcomes of employee engagement: a narrative synthesis", *International Journal of Management Reviews*, Vol. 19 No. 1, pp. 31-53.
- Khalid, M., Rehman, C. A., & Ilyas, M. (2016). HRM practices and employee performance in public sector organizations in Pakistan: An empirical study. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 3(2), 1-13.
- Bakker, A.B. and Albrecht, S. (2018), "Work engagement: current Trends", *Career Development International*, Vol. 23 No. 1, pp. 4-11.
- Bakker, A.B. and Demerouti, E. (2014), "Job demands-resources theory", in Chen, P.Y. and Cooper, C.L. (Eds), *Work and Wellbeing: Wellbeing: A Complete Reference Guide*, John Wiley & Sons, West Sussex, Vol. 3.
- Khalid, M., Rehman, C. A., & Ilyas, M. (2016). HRM practices and employee performance in public sector organizations in Pakistan: An empirical study. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 3(2), 1-13.
- Bakker, A.B., Demerouti, E., Boer, E.D. and Schaufeli, W.B. (2003), "Job demands and job resources as predictors of absence duration and frequency", *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 62 No. 2, pp. 341-356.
- Bal, P.M., Kooij, D.T.A.M. and Jong, S.B.D. (2013), "How do developmental and accommodative HRM enhance employee engagement and commitment? The role of psychological contract and social strategies", *Journal of Management Studies*, Vol. 50 No. 4, pp. 545-571.
- Saleem, I. & Khurshid, A. (2014). Do human resource practices affect employee performance? *International Journal of Management and Social Sciences Research*, 669-688.
- Becker, B.E. and Gerhart, B. (1996), "The impact of human resource management on organizational performance: progress and prospects", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 39 No. 4, pp. 779-801.
- Beijer, S., Peccei, R., Veldhoven, M.v. and Paauwe, J. (2019), "The turn to employees in the measurement of human resource practices: a critical review and proposed way forward", *Human Resource Management Journal*, Vol. Early View, pp. 1-17.
- Bowra, Z. A., Sharif, B., Saeed, A., & Niazi, M. K. (2012). Impact of human

- resource practices on employee perceived performance in banking sector of Pakistan. *African Journal of Business Management*, 6(1), 323-332.
- Boon, C. and Kalshoven, K. (2014), "How high-commitment HRM relates to engagement and commitment: the moderating role of task proficiency", *Human Resource Management*, Vol. 53 No. 3, pp. 403-420.
- Choudhary, G.B. and Puranik, S. (2014), "A study on employee performance appraisal in health care", *Asian Journal of Management Sciences*, Vol. 2 No. 3, pp. 59-64.
- Mahmood, F., Iqbal, N., & Sahu, S. R. (2014). The impact of human resource management practices on employee performance in the banking industry of Pakistan. *Euro-Asian Journal of Economics and Finance*, 2(1), 86-99.
- Conway, E. and Monks, K. (2008), "HR practices and commitment to change: an employee-level analysis", *Human Resource Management Journal*, Vol. 18, pp. 72-89.
- Cooke, F.L., Cooper, B., Bartram, T., Wang, J. and Mei, H. (2019), "Mapping the relationships between high-performance work systems, employee resilience and engagement: a study of the banking industry in China", *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 30 No. 8, pp. 1239-1260.
- Akhtar, A., Nawaz, M. K., Mahmood, Z., & Shahid, M. S. (2016). Impact of high performance work practices on employees' performance in Pakistan: Mediating role of employee engagement. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences (PJCSS)*, 10(3), 708-724.
- Crawford, E.R., LePine, J.A. and Rich, B.L. (2010), "Linking job demands and resources to employee engagement and burnout: a theoretical extension and meta-analytic test", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 95 No. 5, pp. 834-848.
- Daley, D.M. (1986), "Humanistic management and organizational success: the effect of job and work environment characteristics on organizational effectiveness, public responsiveness, and job satisfaction", *Public Personnel Management*, Vol. 15 No. 1, pp. 131-142.
- Hassan, S. (2016). Impact of HRM practices on employee's performance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 6(1), 15-22.

APPENDIX

Items were responded using five-point Likert-type scales with anchors ranging from (1) strongly disagree to (5) strongly agree.

Work Engagement

1. Do you believe that your job inspires you?
2. Does it feel like you're enthusiastic about your job?
3. Do you believe that you feel proud of the work that you do?

Turnover intention

1. Do you believe that you are seriously considering leaving your current job to work at another company?
2. Do you feel a strong urge to quit your job at your current workplace sometimes?
3. Do you think that you are likely to start looking for a new job within the next year?
4. Do you believe there's a high chance you might leave your present job in the next six months?

Performance appraisal Satisfaction

1. Do you feel that your performance rating fairly and accurately reflects your job performance?
2. Does your supervisor's performance appraisal give you a sense of acceptance and satisfaction?
3. Does your supervisor allow you to participate in choosing the goals you are to achieve?
4. Do you feel that the most important parts of your job are highlighted in your performance appraisal?

Pay satisfaction

1. Do you feel content (Satisfied) with your current pay?
2. Do you think the method of determining pay increments is fair?

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